

HE WAS A TEENAGE PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

Meliboeva Nodirakhan Khatamovna

Andijan State University Teacher of the "General Pedagogy" department

Annotation: Parents with teenage children and teenagers themselves often have the following problems that require pedagogical and psychological counseling.

Key word: option, adolescent age, parents, character, educational process.

In general, a teenager is characterized by a high interest in communication with peers, not with adults, within the framework of age-related interests and characteristics. Among their peers, they discuss issues that excite them, but are not relevant to adults. As for adults, they consider such matters that excite teenagers as petty and naive and make them even more bored. In this sense, the humanity of adolescent communication is manifested as a natural, transitory character of age. This phenomenon indicates the curiosity and social psychological growth of the adolescent, as well as their transition from childhood to adulthood.

Option 1. There are constant conflicts between parents and teenage children on various issues.

Option 2. For some reason, teenagers do not want to get an education, they behave like surbets, they do not conscientiously fulfill their duties at home, they do not fulfill their promises to their parents, etc.

Situation 1. In the family, constant conflicts between parents and teenage children are the most common phenomenon. This is natural to some extent. These conflicts are related to the child's higher level of psychological development, the transition from childhood to adulthood, so this situation should not cause special anxiety in parents about their child's future. In contrast to the normative crisis of adolescence, acute interpersonal conflicts lead to a strained relationship with the surrounding people, and this is not considered a normative situation. If such a situation is not eliminated quickly and in time, it will hinder the psychological development of the teenager. For the normal development of a person of any age, it is necessary to have constant, open and reliable interactions with people around them, which have a positive emotional basis. For children, these are interactions with parents, teachers, and peers. After all,

with their help, a teenager can successfully solve difficult internal problems that bother him during the transition period. The methods of solving interpersonal conflicts between parents and adolescents can be different. Adults, that is, parents, should take the initiative in preventing and eliminating such situations. Because they are more competent and intelligent people than teenagers in this emerging conflict situation, they should behave as flexible and thoughtful people in their relationship with teenagers.

2nd situation. This is a social behavior of a teenager that violates the norms and rules of behavior accepted among adults. The maladaptive symptoms associated with this problem are a psychological consequence or reflection of a common adolescent crisis and tend to disappear as the adolescent grows older and changes his or her thinking. However, if the above-mentioned negative signs of adolescent behavior are not actively dealt with, the crisis of adolescence can be prolonged, which leads to the delay of psychological development and later the manifestation of unpleasant character traits in adolescent behavior, which leads to their transformation into life habits. This can be solved by conducting psychological counseling with parents or teachers who turn to a psychologist for the issue under discussion. Then you should work objectively and in detail on the following questions. First, it is necessary to determine in what situations and how quickly socially maladaptive behavior appears in adolescents. Secondly, it is necessary to find out how parents view such behavior of their children. Thirdly, it is determined what results the measures taken by the parents have led to.

Fourthly, it is necessary to know how the teenager explained his behavior to his parents. After analyzing these questions, the psychologist learns about the situation and makes clear and informed decisions as a result of the analysis. In any situation, you should have the following practical recommendations that will help you solve the problem: You should try to stop the negative emotional impact on the adolescent's impulsive actions and behavior, his resistance to the rational judgment of adults. It is necessary to make an objective assessment of what is actually happening, why the teenager behaves this way. It is necessary to get a clear answer to this question that explains the behavior of the teenager, not only explaining but justifying it. It is necessary to find ways to convince the teenager to change his behavior. It is necessary to make a decision and try to change one's beliefs without coercion. It is necessary that he continue to implement his decisive actions until the problem is solved.

In conclusion, it is necessary to abandon the use of methods that were ineffective before exposure to the teenager and caused clear negative reactions from the teenager. Parents should use only positive communication skills with Sabot. Here it is useful for them to be in constant consultation with a psychologist.

References

1. R.S. Nemov "Psychological counseling" pp. 118-124.
2. P.I. Ivanov, M.E. Zufarova - General psychology. Own. FMJ., 2008
3. Ghaziyev EG - General psychology. 1-2 floors. T., Science, 2002.
4. M. G. Davletshin - General psychology. T., TDPU, 2002
5. Абдуллаева, Н. Ж., & Комилова, Ф. М. (2020). Значимость формирования организаторских качеств у будущих учителей в развитии современной педагогики. Наука и образование сегодня, (6-1 (53)), 42-43.
6. Abdullayeva, N. J. (2020). EXPERIENCE AND THEORETICAL BASES OF INTERNAL CONTROL SERVICE ACTIVITIES IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR. Экономика и социум, (5-1 (72)), 13-15.
7. Abdullayeva, N. J. (2020). ISSUES OF REFORMING ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR. Мировая наука, (4 (37)), 6-9.